

Exploring the impact of knowledge potential difference on knowledge transfer performance: An empirical investigation of inventor mobility

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Abstract

Despite the increasing attention paid by scholars and policymakers to inventor mobility and its impact on organizations' knowledge and technology transfer, little is known about how knowledge potential difference (KPD) between original and recruiting organizations affects the knowledge transfer performance (KTP) of inventor mobility. KPD can be measured at both the depth and breadth levels to capture knowledge differences between organizations. Using a sample of 3,257 global inventors identified by linking the EPO's PATSTAT Worldwide Patent Statistical Database and Compustat Database, we investigate how differences in the level of mastery of core knowledge in fixed technology fields (KPD Depth) and understanding of heterogeneous and diverse knowledge (KPD Breadth) between original and recruiting organizations affect KTP activities. We find an inverted U-shaped relationship between the effects of both KPD Depth and KPD Breadth on KTP activities, which suggests that KPD has a significant impact on KTP in the context of inventor mobility. This study provides insights into the factors influencing knowledge transfer in inventor mobility and expands the scope of research on inventor mobility while enriching the research context of knowledge potential difference.

Introduction

In the knowledge-based economy, the competitive advantage of organizations is increasingly dependent on the absorption and application of external knowledge in addition to internal knowledge creation. Collaboration with other organizations is a common means of acquiring such knowledge, but it often fails to be effectively utilized (Kogut & Zander, 1992). Inventor mobility between organizations, however, has become a more prevalent method of accessing external knowledge due to the fast-paced technological advancements, strategic alliances, and market innovation (Ge, Huang, & Kankanhalli, 2020). According to the theory of knowledge embeddedness, inventors, as fundamental components of organizational knowledge systems, transfer their knowledge and experience gained from prior work to the new work environment, thereby facilitating knowledge transfer between organizations. Prior research has emphasized the importance of inventor mobility in promoting knowledge transfer performance (Singh & Agrawal, 2011; Wang & Zatzick, 2019).

Previous research have mainly explored how to improve the effectiveness of individual knowledge transfer from inventors to recruiting organizations through mobility based on the respective attribute characteristics of inventors and recruiting organizations, as well as their interrelationships, such as the social capital of inventors (Ferraris, Santoro, & Scuotto, 2018; Yu & Junshu, 2013), the knowledge depth and breadth of recruiting organizations (Volberda, Foss, & Lyles, 2010), the technical distance, path dependence of the recruiting organization (Song, Almeida, & Wu, 2003) and age of the organization (Jain, 2016); few studies have paid attention to another important participant in the mobility: the original organization. As the place where inventors use their previous knowledge and experience, the knowledge of the original organization largely influences the way inventors construct and use their knowledge, and this influence will accompany the mobility of inventors into the recruiting organization, interact with the knowledge of the recruiting organization, and then influence the innovation activities (Zhou & Li, 2012). Research on collaborative innovation also shows that knowledge mastery and domain differences between organizations significantly affect knowledge transfer (Li & Zhu, 2021; Wei & Limin, 2018).

To address this gap, we develop a conceptual framework on how knowledge potential difference (KPD) between original and recruiting organizations affects the knowledge transfer performance (KTP) of inventor mobility. As an essential concept for describing differences in organizational knowledge distribution, KPD can be measured in two dimensions: depth and breadth (Ryu et al., 2005). The knowledge depth potential difference (KPD Depth) represents the difference in the level of mastery of core knowledge in fixed technology fields by different organizations, while the knowledge breadth potential difference (KPD Breadth) represents the difference in the level of understanding of heterogeneous and diverse knowledge by different organizations (De Luca & Atuahene-Gima, 2007). Combining the relevant definitions of knowledge transfer (Teece, 1977; Martin & Salomon, 2003) and the specific context of this study, we specifically define the KTP as the extent to which the knowledge that can promote technology innovation accumulated by inventors in their past work is acquired, understood and transformed into recruiting knowledge outcomes by the recruiting organization after they leave the original organization and enter the recruiting organization.

To test our theory, we follow previous work and identify inventor mobility by linking EPO's PATSTAT Worldwide Patent Statistical Database and Compustat Database. The former is widely used in research on technological innovation and knowledge management in the field of informetrics and scientometrics (Wada, 2020; Argyres, Rios, & Silverman, 2020), and contains information on global patent titles, abstracts, technology fields, filing dates, inventors, and country affiliations since 1978; the latter contains detailed financial history data for 24,000 public companies registered on U.S. or Canadian exchanges. This study identifies inventor mobility by identifying changes in the organization to which successive patent applications by inventors belong (Almeida & Kogut, 1999; Rosenkopf & Almeida, 2003; Tzabbar, 2009), and measures all variables with patent and company financial data, and probes the relationship between variables through regression models to test the hypotheses proposed.

Our study offers the following contributions to the literature. First, the contribution to the research related to mobility. Previous studies have focused on the binary relationship between inventors and recruiting organizations and analyzed the impact on factors such as knowledge transfer and innovation around the main characteristics of inventors, the main characteristics of recruiting organizations, and the relationship between them. This study expands the research actor to the relationship between original organizations and recruiting organizations and considers the more complex and important KPD as an environmental factor in the KTP.

Second, it contributes to the research related to knowledge transfer. Previous studies mainly discussed knowledge transfer between subjects at the same level from three levels: individual, team, and organizational. Some studies have focused on the process of transferring individual knowledge to organizations (Singh & Agrawal, 2011; Song, Almeida, & Wu, 2003; Tandon, Ertug, & Carnabuci, 2020), but few studies have quantified the knowledge transfer of inventor mobility based on objective patent data representing technological innovation for analysis. Based on objective data, this study enriches the knowledge transfer framework in the inventor mobility process.

Finally, it contributes to the research related to knowledge potential difference. Most of the previous studies only analyze the impact of KPD as a static variable on inter-organizational relationships. In contrast, this study integrates KPD into the dynamic process of inventor mobility and analyzes the impact of KPD on this dynamic process by tracing the characteristics of each innovation subject in this process and the final KTP. It enriches the study of knowledge

potential difference and helps to better understand the mechanism of knowledge potential difference's influence on knowledge transfer, sharing, and creation.

Theoretical framework and hypotheses

Knowledge transfer performance in the inventor mobility

This study focuses on the performance of individual knowledge transfer from inventors to recruiting organizations in the process of inventor mobility. Due to different research perspectives and contexts, the definition of "knowledge transfer through human mobility" varies greatly among scholars. Therefore, it is necessary to sort out the existing relevant studies to clarify the existing research contents and methods in this direction.

A sizeable stream of literature has shown that inventors, as the basic elements of organizational knowledge systems, apply their knowledge, methods, and experience accumulated in the past to the new environment when mobility occurs, which in turn drives the knowledge innovation activities of the recruiting organization (Singh & Agrawal, 2011; Filatotchev, Liu, Lu, & Wright, 2011; Slavova, Fosfuri, & De Castro, 2016; Jain, 2016). In this process, the original organization, which is the source of existing skills of inventors, cultivates and trains the mobile inventors, so its knowledge level, characteristics, and relationship with the recruiting organization also have considerable influence on the knowledge transfer performance (KTP) of inventor mobility; some studies suggest that inventor mobility is an important mechanism to promote knowledge diffusion between organizations (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). when developmental competition exists between original and recruiting organizations, bringing in inventors from competitors is a common means of acquiring knowledge and rapidly improving organizational capabilities (Fahrenkopf & Argote, 2020).

Although it is obvious that the relationship between the original organization and the recruiting organization has an impact on KTP, few studies have analyzed it as the main object of study. Existing studies have focused more on the impact of mobility itself (Liu & Hu, 2022; Momeni et al., 2022; Wang & Zheng, 2022; Yin & Zong, 2022) or further analyzed the impact of the respective attributes of mobility and the recruiting organization and the dichotomous relationship between them (Ferraris, Santoro, & Scuotto, 2018; Yu & Junshu, 2013; Volberda, Foss, & Lyles, 2010; Song, Almeida, & Wu, 2003). In the first category of studies, scholars have proposed different methods to measure the performance of knowledge transfer, such as measuring the number of publications output and research collaborations of research-oriented inventors (Liu & Hu, 2022), the number of patents output and the number of citations of technology-oriented inventors (Singh & Agrawal, 2011). In the second category of studies, scholars focus on influencing factors such as the type of mobility (Uhlbach, Tartari, & Kongsted, 2022; Zhao et al., 2020; Robinson-Garcia et al., 2019), the purpose of mobility (Wagner & Goossen, 2018), the social capital of inventors (Ferraris, Santoro, & Scuotto, 2018; Yu & Junshu, 2013), the knowledge depth and breadth of recruiting organizations (Volberda, Foss, & Lyles, 2010), the technical distance between the inventor and recruiting organization, path dependence of the recruiting organization (Song, Almeida, & Wu, 2003), etc. While this study focuses on the impact of the relationship between original and recruiting organizations on KTP, it is necessary to develop a new theoretical model for empirical analysis to enrich the existing body of knowledge transfer research on inventor mobility.

Knowledge potential difference in the inventor mobility

Knowledge potential difference (KPD) can reflect the difference in the ability to understand and apply knowledge and technological innovation between different innovation subjects, also known as the gap between knowledge potentials, which can be defined in two dimensions of

depth and breadth (Ryu et al.,2005). This study focuses on the KPD between the original and the recruiting organization in inventor mobility. In terms of depth, the KPD between the original and the recruiting organization in terms of the level of mastery of core knowledge in fixed technology fields, and terms of breadth, the difference between the original and the recruiting organization in terms of mastering knowledge in different fields (Ryu et al.,2005; De Luca & Atuahene-Gima, 2007). The two aspects together reflect the different characteristics of the original and recruiting organizations in the dimensions of knowledge level, knowledge preference, and knowledge acquisition methods. From a static perspective, the KPD between organizations is relative, and an organization with low knowledge potential in one flow process may be an organization with high knowledge potential in another flow process; while from a dynamic perspective, with the influence of complex factors such as organizational development, inventor mobility and breakthrough innovation, an organization with low knowledge potential may become an organization with high knowledge potential in the field, while the organizations that were in high knowledge potential may also be gradually eliminated.

KPD commonly exists between innovation agents as a condition for knowledge transfer and has an important impact on KTP and corporate collaborative innovation (Ensign et al., 2014; Falvey, Foster, & Greenaway, 2007). Existing studies on KPD have focused on two areas, knowledge management, and technological innovation, and have analyzed the mechanisms of KPD among innovation agents on factors such as knowledge transfer, knowledge sharing, and technological innovation at different levels, such as team, organization, industry, and country (Li & Chen, 2010; Wei & Limin, 2018; Tortoriello, Reagans, & McEvily, 2012).

The existence of KPD makes a potential energy similar to the "field" in physics exist between organizations, which will maintain and promote continuous knowledge sharing and transfer in the relevant range of organizations to improve the overall knowledge potential. Therefore, this study argues that in the knowledge transfer process of inventor mobility, there are also different levels of absorption and application of transferred knowledge due to different inter-organizational KPD, resulting in different knowledge transfer performances for inventors with the same conditions. Related studies also suggest that the inter-organizational KPD is the main driving force for inter-organizational inventor mobility and knowledge transfer, and it is because of the inter-organizational KPD that there is a continuous exchange of knowledge, technology and personnel between organizations, and thus the overall knowledge stock is continuously improved (Brettel & Cleven, 2011; Ensign et al., 2014). Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual schematic of knowledge transfer and KPD of inventor mobility.

Figure 1. Inventor mobility framework

Knowledge depth potential difference and knowledge transfer performance

When the knowledge depth potential difference (KPD Depth) in the mobility process is small, if the inventor chooses an organization with higher knowledge depth potential for mobility, further expanding the KPD Depth with the original organization will facilitate the inventor's development and more opportunities for skill development after entering the recruiting organization, and promote knowledge transfer performance. On the one hand, the increase of KPD Depth means that the recruiting organization invests more resources and human cost for exploring and absorbing specific knowledge (Iorio, Labory, & Rentocchini, 2017), and inventors have the opportunity to contact more relevant technical workers and deeper technical knowledge environment after entering the recruiting organization, and can effectively integrate their knowledge into the new environment through communication and exchange. On the other hand, technology R&D activities are a kind of high-risk and high-investment enterprise strategic behavior, and the recruiting organization occupies a higher knowledge potential means that it also needs more external knowledge sources to achieve technological breakthroughs (Phene, Madhok, & Liu, 2015), so the organization with high knowledge potential tends to pay more attention to absorbing and learning knowledge from new incoming inventors to improve its own knowledge performance.

However, when the KPD Depth gradually increases to a certain threshold, further increasing the KPD Depth between the original and the recruiting organization may lead to the formation of knowledge barriers between inventors and the recruiting organization to prevent the absorption and transformation of knowledge and reduce the efficiency of inventors' participation in technology research and development after entering the recruiting organization, which is not conducive to knowledge transfer (Phene, Madhok, & Liu, 2015). The formation of such knowledge barriers may come from the gradually increasing differences in knowledge and cognitive bases between inventors and recruiting organizations, which increase the cost and burden of exchange and communication between the two parties, thus negatively affecting knowledge transfer (Grover, Lim, & Ayyagari, 2006). At the same time, with the further increase of knowledge potential difference in the flow process, the norms and standards of the recruiting organization in managing its technology R&D team will further increase, and due to the expansion of the system and team size, the role that new inventors can play after entering the organization will be gradually compressed, and their value will gradually be replaced by the overall value of the team step by step, which leads to the reduction of knowledge that inventors can transfer from the original organization. The knowledge transfer performance is inhibited by the reduction of knowledge that inventors can transfer from the original organization. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis (H1): There is an inverted U-shaped relationship between the KPD Depth and the knowledge transfer performance of inventor mobility.

Knowledge breadth potential difference and knowledge transfer performance

When the knowledge breadth potential difference (KPD Breadth) in the mobility process is small, if inventors choose organizations with higher knowledge breadth potential, further expanding the KPD Breadth with the original organization will facilitate the inventors' development and get more opportunities to develop their skills after entering the recruiting organization, and promote knowledge transfer. On the one hand, different organizations have their uniqueness in key technology fields, technology R&D environment, reward systems, team atmosphere, etc. As the KPD Breadth increases, the recruiting organization will continue to increase its ability to absorb and receive diversified knowledge (Kim, Lee, & Cho, 2016), and the more it can absorb and learn various knowledge and skills from the incoming inventors in

their original organizations, and put them into the new technology R&D activities as the resource advantage of their own R&D. On the other hand, the higher the knowledge breadth of the organization means that it tends to complement its knowledge base (Watanabe, Hur, & Matsumoto, 2005), and the absorption and use of different knowledge from new inventors to promote its technological development are in line with the knowledge characteristics of the recruiting organization.

However, when the KPD Breadth of mobility gradually increases to a certain threshold, the knowledge that individuals can grasp and carry is ultimately relatively single compared with the greater knowledge breadth level of the organization, so the diversified knowledge system will gradually disperse the technical R&D resources that inventors can use, and exceed the benefit of high absorption capacity brought by the diversified knowledge system, and instead inhibit the absorption capacity of the recruiting organization to the knowledge transferred from inventors. The recruiting organization's ability to absorb the knowledge transferred from the inventor is inhibited (Morone & Taylor, 2004). Moreover, an excessive knowledge breadth will bring more uncertainty and negative cooperation to the organization's technology R&D environment, and most of the technology R&D activities may not be truly implemented and knowledge transformed in the end, and it will also increase the cost of managing the technology team, thus reducing the absorption of individual inventors' knowledge (Storbacka et al., 2016). Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis (H2): There is an inverted U-shaped relationship between the KPD Breadth and the knowledge transfer performance of inventor mobility.

Figure 2. Research model

Data and methods

Overview of data and sources

This study uses patent data to measure knowledge transfer in inventor mobility, using EPO's PATSTAT Worldwide Patent Statistical Database (2020 Autumn Edition). PATSTAT is widely used in research on technological innovation and knowledge management in the field of informetrics and scientometrics (Wada, 2020; Argyres, Rios, & Silverman, 2020), and contains information on patent titles, abstracts, technology fields, filing dates, inventors, and countries since 1978. By counting the patent applicants in PATSTAT, we can obtain the patent application status of the organization's subjects and measure the technical characteristics of the organization. However, the patents of some organizations in PATSTAT are assigned to different organization primary keys due to organization name modification, or parent-subsidiary applications, resulting in some errors in the measurement of organization characteristics. To solve this problem, this study disambiguates the organization subjects by linking the PATSTAT and Compustat database, which contains detailed financial history data

of 24,000 listed companies registered in the U.S. or Canadian exchanges, and previous studies have linked the two with patent information to provide the disambiguation results (Bessen, 2008) Based on the results of PATSTAT organization disambiguation after company primary key alignment, it is possible to combine the primary keys of different organizations that are the same organization, thus providing more accurate statistics on organizational patent data applications for inventor mobility identification and empirical studies.

Identification of inventor mobility

Based on the cleaned data, this study identifies the inventor mobility by identifying the change of the organization to which the inventor belongs for successive patent applications, which is reflected in the data as an inventor making patent applications in a certain organization for a successive time; and starting from a certain patent application, the organization to which the patent application belongs changes. Inventor mobility occurs between two patent applications where the organization to which the inventor belongs has changed.

According to the previous research, we estimate the mobility time as the middle value of the two patent application times (Singh & Agrawal, 2011), and clean the mobility data according to the number of mobility, flow patterns, patent features, technical age, and other indicators, including (1) only one mobility record exists for the same inventor, to eliminate the abnormal mobility data caused by patent cooperation, name ambiguity, and other data problems; (2) the original and recruiting organizations for the movement of technical staff must be disambiguated by association with the COMPUSTAT database to ensure the accuracy of the measurement of organizational characteristics; (3) to leave a sufficient observation window for the measurement of the knowledge transfer performance after the inventors' mobility, we limited the time of mobility to the period between 1996 and 2010. Finally, 3,257 mobility records were obtained, involving information on 3,257 inventors and 718 organizations. The methodological framework for the identification of inventor mobility is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Inventor mobility identification method

Measurement

Dependent variable

Knowledge Transfer Performance (KTP): In measuring the *KTP* by using patent data, previous studies mainly measured the knowledge transfer result and the knowledge transfer process, among which the knowledge transfer result can be divided into two aspects: the degree of ownership and the degree of application of the transferred knowledge by the knowledge recipient. Under the perspective of inventor mobility, when individual knowledge of inventors enters the R&D environment of a recruiting organization, the measurement of its *KTP* is mainly based on the quality and quantity of knowledge provided by the inventors for the technological R&D of the recruiting organization, and the more the knowledge provided by inventors is utilized by the organization, the better the effect of knowledge transfer. When discussing related issues, previous authors pointed out that patent citations can indicate the transfer and utilization of technical knowledge to a certain extent (Duguet & MacGarvie, 2005). Therefore, this study uses the citations of the recruiting organization's previous patents to the inventors after the mobility to measure the *KTP*. Specifically, taking the mobility of inventors in year t as an example, the number of citations of the new patents applied by the recruiting organization to all the patents of inventors within 5 years (t to $t + 4$ years) after the mobility is taken as the *KTP*. The higher the number of citations, the more the recruiting organization owns and applies the knowledge transferred by inventors, and the better the knowledge transfer performance.

Independent variables

Knowledge Depth Potential Difference (KPD Depth): The *KPD Depth* of the mobility is calculated using the ratio of the knowledge depth of the recruiting organization and the original organization in the 5 years before the occurrence of mobility. Referring to the calculation method of knowledge depth defined by previous studies (Soete, 1987; Cantwell & Piscitello, 2000), first, the Revealed Technological Advantage (RTA) of each of the original organization and the recruiting organization is calculated with the following formula:

$$RTA_{it} = \frac{\left(\frac{p_{it}}{\sum_i p_{it}} \right)}{\left(\frac{\sum_i p_{it}}{\sum_{it} p_{it}} \right)}$$

This study distinguishes the different layers of technology fields by identifying the three-digit IPC classification numbers of patents. p_{it} is the number of patents filed by an organization i in the technology field t in the 5 years before the mobility occurred. RTA_{it} measures the ratio of the share of the organization i 's patents belonging to the technology field t to the share of all patents in that technology field. If RTA_{it} is greater than 1, it means that organization i is relatively strong in the technology field t . If RTA_{it} is less than 1, it means that organization i is relatively weak in the technology field t . Second, the coefficient of variation of all RTA values for each organization in the corresponding time window is calculated as follows:

$$KD\ Depth_i = \frac{\sigma_{RTA}}{\mu_{RTA}}$$

The σ_{RTA} in the above equation is the standard deviation of the RTA values for all technical fields of organization i , and μ_{RTA} is its mean value. When the organization has a higher RTA value in some technology fields, it represents a higher depth of knowledge in that organization. Finally, the ratio of the depth of knowledge between the recruiting organization and the original

organization during the flow process in the 5 years before the mobility occurred is calculated to obtain the *KPD Depth*:

$$KPD\ Depth = \frac{KD\ Depth_{new}}{KD\ Depth_{old}}$$

$KD\ Depth_{new}$ indicates the knowledge depth of the recruiting organization, and $KD\ Depth_{old}$ indicates the knowledge depth of the original organization. When the *KPD Depth* is greater than 1, it means that the recruiting organization has higher knowledge depth than the original organization; when the knowledge depth potential difference is less than 1, it means that the original organization has higher knowledge depth than the recruiting organization. The more the *KPD Depth* is greater than 1, or the closer to 0, the more significant the difference in knowledge depth between the recruiting organization and the original organization.

Knowledge Breadth Potential Difference (KPD Breadth): The knowledge breadth potential of the mobility is calculated using the ratio of the knowledge breadth of the recruiting organization to the knowledge breadth of the original organization in the 5 years before the mobility, and the knowledge breadth is calculated using the number of patents filed by the organization involving three IPC classification numbers to indicate the knowledge breadth of the organization (Zhang & Baden-Fuller, 2010):

$$KPD\ Breadth = \frac{IPC\ Count_{new}}{IPC\ Count_{old}}$$

$IPC\ Count_{new}$ indicates the knowledge breadth of the recruiting organization, and $IPC\ Count_{old}$ indicates the knowledge breadth of the original organization. When *KPD Breadth* is greater than 1, it means that the recruiting organization has a wider knowledge breadth than the original organization; when *KPD Breadth* is less than 1, it means that the original organization has a wider knowledge breadth than the recruiting organization. The greater the *KPD Breadth* is than 1, or the closer it is to 0, the greater the difference in knowledge breadth between the recruiting organization and the original organization.

Control variables

Since the dependent variable measures the extent of utilization of knowledge transferred by inventors only at the recruiting organization level, which may be influenced by other factors in the recruiting organization environment, *the number of recruiting organization patents (OP)*, *the average number of recruiting organization patent families (OF)*, *the average number of recruiting organization patents cited (OC)*, *the total recruiting organization assets (OA)*, and *the number of recruiting organization employees (OE)* are put into the model as control variables. *OP* is the logarithm of the total number of patents of the recruiting organization before mobility, *OF* is the average number of patent families of all the patents of the recruiting organization before mobility, and *OC* is the average number of citations of all the patents of the recruiting organization before mobility. These three indicators are generally considered to reflect the technological innovation capability of the organization. The larger these indicators are, the more resources the organization can invest in technological R&D and patent innovation, and to a certain extent, they will affect the way the knowledge of new inventors entering the organization is utilized. The data used to calculate *OA* and *OE* come from the Compustat database and take the value of the year before mobility, reflecting the management level and the scale of the organization. Generally speaking, organizations with larger volumes have a set of standardized processes and standards for technology R&D, as well as more diversified ways of acquiring external knowledge, which will affect the absorption of inventors' knowledge under the same conditions.

At the level of inventors themselves, *inventors' technological breadth (TTB)*, *knowledge intermediacy (TI)*, *working age (TA)*, and *technological distance (TD)* between inventors and the recruiting organization will all affect to some extent the recruiting organization's attitude toward their transferred knowledge. *TTD* refers to the degree of distribution of inventors' knowledge; the higher the degree of technological breadth, the stronger their differentiated competitive advantage, measured by the number of three IPC classification numbers of all their patents before mobility. *TI* refers to the network centrality characteristics built up by the knowledge itself in the patents owned by inventors. The stronger the centrality, the more important the inventor occupies in the technology field, which is calculated as the average of the centrality of the knowledge elements corresponding to all the patents of the inventor before mobility in the patent technology network of the corresponding field. *TTB* and *TI* indicate the characteristics of knowledge transferred by inventors, while the *TD* between inventors and recruiting organizations indicates the degree of similarity between the knowledge possessed by inventors and recruiting organizations, and the more similar the knowledge is, the stronger the connection between the two parties. The specific variables are calculated in Table 1.

Table 1. Variable description

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Description</i>
Dependent Variable	
KTP	The number of citations the inventor receives from the recruiting organization within 5 years of joining the organization.
Independent Variables	
KPD Depth	The proportion of knowledge depth between the recruiting and the original organization within 5 years before mobility. The depth of knowledge is the ratio of the standard deviation and the average value of the organization's RTA, which is the ratio of the number of patents in a certain technological field to the total number of patents in the organization and the number of patents in that technological field to the total number of patents in the same period.
KPD Breadth	The proportion of the number of three-digit IPC classification numbers involved in patents filed by the recruiting organization and the original organization within 5 years before mobility.
Control Variables	
OP	The logarithm of the total number of patents of the recruiting organization before mobility.
OF	The average number of patent families for all patents of a recruiting organization before mobility.
OC	The average number of citations of all patents of recruiting organization mobility.
OA	Total assets of the recruiting organization in the year before mobility.
OE	The number of employees in the recruiting organization in the year before mobility.
TTB	The number of three-digit IPC classification numbers for all of its patents before mobility.
TI	The average value of the centrality of the knowledge elements corresponding to all patents in the corresponding domain's patent technology network before mobility.

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Description</i>
TA	The number of years between the year the inventor moves and the year his/her first patent application is filed.
	the degree of similarity between the knowledge possessed by inventors and recruiting organizations. The specific formula is:
	$TD = 1 - \frac{\sum_t p_{mt}p_{newt}}{\sqrt{\sum_t p_{mt}^2 \sum_t p_{newt}^2}}$
TD	<i>m</i> denotes an inventor, <i>new</i> denotes a recruiting organization, <i>t</i> denotes a technical field divided by a three-digit IPC, and <i>p</i> denotes the number of patents.

Results

Descriptive findings

Table 2 presents the means, standard deviations, VIF values, correlation coefficients, and significance of the variables in this study. The VIF values of all variables are less than 4, indicating weak multicollinearity among the variables in this study. The correlation coefficients between the variables indicate that there is no strong correlation between the independent variables. In the sample of inventor mobility data obtained through patent data, the mean value of the number of times that all patents of inventors were cited by new patents filed in the recruiting organization within 5 years after their mobility was 1.45, the mean value of the *KPD Depth* in the mobility process was 1.23, and the mean value of the *KPD Breadth* was 2.32, indicating that most inventors' mobility chose a recruiting organization with higher knowledge depth and breadth than the original organization, and obtained at least one patent citation after mobility. The standard deviation value of knowledge depth potential (0.63) is much smaller than that of knowledge breadth potential (5.06), indicating that mobility is characterized by greater variation in knowledge breadth compared to knowledge depth.

The dependent variable of this study, *KTP*, is a count variable, measuring the frequency of patent citations, and takes the value of the non-negative integer, so it is not appropriate to use ordinary linear regression. And Poisson regression, as a classical counting regression model, has been widely used in empirical studies to study technological innovation and knowledge transfer through patents (Maurseth & Verspagen, 2002; Mehta, Rysman, & Simcoe, 2010). Meanwhile, considering that the standard deviation and mean values of the dependent variable *KTP* in the descriptive statistics of Table 2 are not so different that excessive dispersion is not easy to occur, the empirical estimation will be analyzed by Poisson regression.

Table 2. Correlations and descriptive statistics

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>VIF</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1. <i>KTP</i>	1.45	3.09		1.00											
2. <i>KPD Depth</i>	1.23	0.63	1.41	0.02	1.00										
3. <i>KPD Breadth</i>	2.32	5.06	1.27	0.03*	0.25**	1.00									
4. <i>OP</i>	8.40	2.37	2.98	-0.01**	0.06**	0.11	1.00								
5. <i>OF</i>	18.48	10.16	1.89	0.04**	-0.06**	0.10**	0.64**	1.00							
6. <i>OC</i>	3.87	3.42	1.19	0.04**	0.01	0.00	-0.11**	-0.13**	1.00						
7. <i>OA</i>	8.63	2.99	1.92	-0.02	0.01	0.14**	0.63**	0.42**	0.07**	1.00					

Variable	Mean	SD	VIF	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
8. OE	65.27	91.26	1.98	-0.08***	-0.11***	0.10***	0.62***	0.32***	-0.20***	0.53***	1.00				
9. TTB	2.93	2.30	1.40	0.05***	-0.06***	-0.04***	0.07***	0.11***	-0.14***	0.02	0.04	1.00			
10. TI	0.17	0.30	1.07	-0.03	0.03*	0.05**	-0.11**	-0.11***	0.03	-0.03	-0.05*	-0.18***	1.00		
11. TA	2.88	2.79	1.17	-0.01	0.01	-0.04*	0.16***	0.05**	-0.04*	0.05**	0.08***	0.33***	-0.14***	1.00	
12. TD	0.45	0.37	1.11	0.15***	-0.01	0.02	0.06**	0.12***	0.14***	0.11***	-0.08*	0.05**	-0.04*	0.02	1.00

Note: *, **, *** respectively represent $p < 0.1$, $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, the same below.

Regression results

Table 3 shows the results of the two dimensions of knowledge potential difference (depth and breadth) on knowledge transfer performance. Model 2 incorporates the control variable, the independent variable *KPD Depth*, and its squared term. The results show that the coefficient of the *KPD Depth* is 0.31 and the coefficient of its squared term is -0.05, and both are significant at the 1% level. The turning point of the inverted U-shape is 3.1 ($0.31/2*0.05$), which lies within the range of the *KPD Depth* [0.074, 12.52], proving the inverted U-shape relationship on the *KTP* that the *KPD Depth* first promotes and then inhibits the *KTP* of inventor mobility. the hypothesis H1 holds. When the *KPD Depth* of the mobility reaches 3.1, it indicates that the knowledge depth of the recruiting organization is 3.1 times that of the original organization, and if this ratio continues to increase it will lead to a decrease in the amount of knowledge used and absorbed by the organization after inventors enter the recruiting organization. Combining with Table 2, we can see that the mean value of the *KPD Depth* is 1.23, which indicates that most of the inventors in the sample can still choose the recruiting organization with larger knowledge depth to further improve the efficiency of knowledge transfer after they enter the recruiting organization and play a greater technical value.

Model 3 incorporates the control variables, the independent variable *KPD Breadth*, and its squared term. The results show that the coefficient of the *KPD Breadth* is 0.05 and the coefficient of its squared term is -0.001, and both are significant at the 1% level. Its inverted U-shaped turning point is 25 ($0.05/2*0.001$), which lies within the value range [0.0078, 91.25] of the *KPD Breadth*, proving the inverted U-shape relationship on the *KTP* that the *KPD Breadth* first promotes and then inhibits the *KTP* of inventor mobility. Hypothesis H2 holds. Specifically, when the knowledge breadth of the recruiting organization is more than 25 times that of the original organization, the larger the *KPD Breadth*, the more the recruiting organization knows in unfamiliar fields for inventors, which will lead to a decrease in the effect of inventor knowledge transfer. Combined with the mean value of knowledge breadth potential difference of 2.32 for the sample inventor mobility data, it can be seen that the vast majority of inventor mobility has a *KPD Breadth* below the turning point, indicating that there is still room for existing mobility to flow to higher knowledge breadth organizations to further improve the efficiency of knowledge transfer. Model 4 incorporates the control variables, *KPD Depth*, *KPD Breadth*, and their respective squared terms simultaneously, and the coefficients of the quadratic terms are all significant at the 1% level, further verifying the robustness of the main effect inverted U-shaped relationship in this study.

Based on a sufficient sample size, the present Poisson regression model exhibits a moderate level of fit, as assessed by both the coefficient estimates and the size of the conditional R-squared. However, further testing is necessary to assess the validity of the inverted U-shaped effect. To this end, the Standardized Mean Difference (SMD) effect size, as proposed by Cohen (1988), was used to examine the inverted U-shaped effects of *KPD Depth* and *KPD Breadth* on *KTP*. The SMD of *KPD Depth* is 0.226 (95% CI [0.086, 0.393]), indicating a significant and

positive effect. The SMD of *KPD Depth*² is -0.04 (95% CI [-0.066, -0.012]), indicating a significant and negative effect. Considering the values of SMD of the original value and squared terms of *KPD Depth* together, the inverted U-shaped effect of *KPD Depth* on *KTP* remains significant. The SMD of *KPD Breadth* is 0.04 (95% CI [0.029, 0.05]), indicating a significant and positive effect. The SMD of *KPD Breadth*² is -0.001 (95% CI [-0.001, 0]), indicating a significant and negative effect. Although the effect sizes for *KPD Breadth* are relatively small, considering the sample size and p-value, the inverted U-shaped effect of *KPD Breadth* on *KTP* remains significant.

Table 3. Regression results

Variable	Dependent variable: <i>KTP</i>			
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>KPD Depth</i>		0.31*** (0.07)		0.23*** (0.07)
<i>KPD Depth</i> ²		-0.05*** (0.02)		-0.05*** (0.02)
<i>KPD Breadth</i>			0.05*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)
<i>KPD Breadth</i> ²			-0.001*** (0.0002)	-0.001*** (0.0001)
<i>OP</i>	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000*** (0.0000)	0.0000*** (0.0000)
<i>OF</i>	0.01*** (0.002)	0.01*** (0.002)	0.01*** (0.002)	0.01*** (0.002)
<i>OC</i>	0.01*** (0.004)	0.02*** (0.004)	0.01*** (0.004)	0.01*** (0.004)
<i>OA</i>	-0.01** (0.01)	-0.02*** (0.01)	-0.02*** (0.01)	-0.02*** (0.01)
<i>OE</i>	-0.002*** (0.0003)	-0.002*** (0.0003)	-0.003*** (0.0003)	-0.002*** (0.0003)
<i>TTB</i>	0.04*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)
<i>TI</i>	-0.12** (0.05)	-0.13** (0.05)	-0.16*** (0.05)	-0.16*** (0.05)
<i>TA</i>	-0.02*** (0.01)	-0.03*** (0.01)	-0.02*** (0.01)	-0.02*** (0.01)
<i>TD</i>	0.79*** (0.04)	0.79*** (0.04)	0.80*** (0.04)	0.80*** (0.04)
Constant	-0.10* (0.06)	-0.38*** (0.08)	-0.12** (0.06)	-0.31*** (0.08)
Sample size	3,257	3,257	3,257	3,257
Conditional R ²	0.19	0.20	0.21	0.22
Akaike Inf. Crit.	16,128.00	16,097.00	16,042.00	16,032.00

Note: The standard errors are shown in brackets, the same as below.

For the control variables, in Models 1 to 4, the coefficients of *TD* and *TTB* are both significantly positive at the 1% level, indicating that the greater the technical distance between inventors and recruiting organizations, the lower the technical similarity, the higher the level of the technical breadth of inventors, and the higher the degree of absorption and utilization of their transferred knowledge by recruiting organizations. The *TI* and *TA* of inventors are significantly negative above the 5% level, indicating that the *KTP* with lower knowledge intermediacy and younger technical age is better, which may be due to the rapid iterative characteristics of patent technology development, resulting in new knowledge often coming from newcomers in the industry and such knowledge still does not have higher knowledge intermediacy in the technology field network due to the short period. At the organizational level, the effects of *OP*, *OF*, and *OC* are all significantly positive, indicating that the level of recruiting organizations in technology R&D affects their ability to absorb and use external knowledge from the inventor. In contrast, the variables of *OA* and *OE* representing organization size have a significantly negative effect on knowledge transfer, indicating that organizations with smaller organization sizes may absorb and use more knowledge from the introduced new inventors due to limited external knowledge sources and limitations in the technology R&D model.

Robustness test

The above regression results verify the hypothesis proposed in this study to a certain extent, but in the research and development work after the actual mobility, there are cases where inventors cite their previously published patent achievements in the patent research and development work they participate in. Figure 4 shows the distribution of this self-citation phenomenon in the data sample of this study. Figure 4(a) shows that there are 331 cases of self-citation of patents cited by recruiting organizations after the inventors moved out of the 3,257 flow records, accounting for 10.16%, with the highest number of self-citations reaching 13. Figure 4(b) shows that of the 331 data samples in which self-citation occurs, 114 have self-citation accounting for 100% of all citations, and 69 have self-citation accounting for more than 50%. These self-citations are also calculated within the KTP, but the inventor self-citation cannot provide too much information representing knowledge transfer as non-self-citation, which may cause a certain error in the regression result. Therefore, the reference times of all patents of the inventors are regressed by replacing the dependent variable with the new patents applied for by the recruiting organization within 5 years after the deletion of self-citation, and the results are shown in Table 4. It can be found that in model 6 and model 7, the effect of *KPD Depth* and *KPD Breadth* on *KTP except self-citation* is still an inverted U-shaped relationship, i.e., hypothesis H1 and hypothesis H2 still hold.

Figure 4. self-citation in measuring the KTP

Table 4. Robustness test with substitution dependent variable

Variable	Dependent variable: <i>KTP except for self-citation</i>			
	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8
KPD Depth		0.32*** (0.07)		0.25*** (0.07)
KPD Depth ²		-0.05*** (0.02)		-0.05** (0.02)
KPD Breadth			0.05*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)
KPD Breadth ²			-0.001*** (0.0002)	-0.001*** (0.0002)

OP	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000* (0.0000)	0.0000* (0.0000)
OF	0.01*** (0.002)	0.01*** (0.002)	0.01*** (0.002)	0.01*** (0.002)
OC	0.01 (0.005)	0.01* (0.005)	0.01 (0.005)	0.01 (0.005)
OA	-0.01** (0.01)	-0.02*** (0.01)	-0.02*** (0.01)	-0.02*** (0.01)
OE	-0.002*** (0.0004)	-0.002*** (0.0004)	-0.002*** (0.0004)	-0.002*** (0.0004)
TTB	0.04*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)
TI	-0.22*** (0.06)	-0.23*** (0.06)	-0.25*** (0.06)	-0.26*** (0.06)
TA	-0.02*** (0.01)	-0.03*** (0.01)	-0.02*** (0.01)	-0.02*** (0.01)
TD	0.89*** (0.04)	0.89*** (0.04)	0.90*** (0.04)	0.90*** (0.04)
Constant	-0.29*** (0.06)	-0.59*** (0.08)	-0.31*** (0.06)	-0.53*** (0.08)
Sample size	3,257	3,257	3,257	3,257
Conditional R ²	0.19	0.20	0.21	0.21
Akaike Inf. Crit.	14,702.25	14,669.12	14,631.48	14,619.11

To enhance the reliability of the robustness test, we further use the sub-sample method to validate. It is found that there is a special situation in the inventor mobility, that is, the patent applied for by the inventor has been cited by the recruiting organization before entering the recruiting organization, which means that the inventor has a certain technical connection with the recruiting organization before mobility. It may be precise because of this connection that the inventor leaves the original organization and move to the recruiting organization, which may affect the *KTP*. The recruiting organization may increase the efficiency of knowledge transfer by paying more attention to inventors who have technical connections before they move. Out of all 3,257 mobility events selected in this study, there are 295 mobility events for which patents were cited by recruiting organizations before mobility, as shown in Figure 5. Figure 5(a) shows that there are 188 mobility events with more than 2 citations out of 295 mobility events, with a maximum of 33 citations. However, Figure 5(b) shows the boxplot chart of the distribution of *KTP* of the two types of mobility events. the average number of times cited after mobility is 1.22 for the inventors who have no technical association with the recruiting organization before, while the average number of times cited after the flow is 3.74 for the inventors who have a technical association with the recruiting organization before, which is significantly higher than the former, indicating that the prior ties before the flow will affect the *KTP* after mobility. Therefore, this study performed regression analysis again using the remaining 2,962 flow records by removing these data samples that were cited before, and the results are shown in Table 5. It can be found that in model 10 and model 11, the effect of *KPD Depth* and *KPD Breadth* on *KTP* is still an inverted U-shaped relationship, i.e., hypothesis H1 and hypothesis H2 still hold. Through the above two robustness test results, it is shown that the regression results of our study are robust.

Figure 5. Sample distribution about citation before mobility

Table 5. Robustness test with sub-sample regression

Variable	Dependent variable: KTP			
	Model 9	Model 10	Model 11	Model 12
KPD Depth		0.25*** (0.08)		0.16** (0.08)
KPD Depth ²		-0.04** (0.02)		-0.04** (0.02)
KPD Breadth			0.05*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)
KPD Breadth ²			-0.001*** (0.0001)	-0.001*** (0.0001)
OP	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000** (0.0000)	0.0000** (0.0000)
OF	0.01*** (0.002)	0.01*** (0.002)	0.01*** (0.002)	0.01*** (0.002)
OC	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.004 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)
OA	-0.04*** (0.01)	-0.04*** (0.01)	-0.04*** (0.01)	-0.04*** (0.01)
OE	-0.002*** (0.0004)	-0.002*** (0.0004)	-0.002*** (0.0004)	-0.002*** (0.0004)
TTB	0.04*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)
TI	-0.05 (0.06)	-0.05 (0.06)	-0.08 (0.06)	-0.08 (0.06)
TA	-0.05*** (0.01)	-0.05*** (0.01)	-0.04*** (0.01)	-0.04*** (0.01)
TD	0.89*** (0.04)	0.89*** (0.04)	0.90*** (0.04)	0.90*** (0.04)
Constant	0.66*** (0.05)	0.66*** (0.05)	0.67*** (0.05)	0.66*** (0.05)
Sample size	2,962	2,962	2,962	2,962
Akaike Inf. Crit.	13,283.15	13,271.17	13,203.17	13,202.01

Discussion and conclusion

Research conclusions

This study presents an empirical investigation of the mechanisms underlying depth and breadth of knowledge potential difference (KPD) between the original and recruiting organization on inventor mobility's Knowledge Transfer Performance (KTP). Utilizing patent and enterprise data spanning from 1996 to 2010, we employed the Poisson regression method to model the relationships. The robustness of our results was verified by the robustness test. Our research findings indicate that both KPD Depth and KPD Breadth exhibit an inverted U-shaped effect on the KTP of inventor mobility. That is when the KPD Depth of the recruiting organization into which inventors mobility is below the critical value compared with that of the original organization, the promotion effect of the KTP due to more external knowledge demand brought about by the increased knowledge depth of the recruiting organization is much greater than the suppression effect of the knowledge barrier formed by the increased depth, but when the KPD

Depth continues to increase beyond the critical value, the effect size of these two relationships will reverse. Similarly, when the KPD Breadth of the recruiting organization to which the inventor's mobility is below the critical value, the promotion effect of the KTP due to the ability to absorb and apply more diverse knowledge brought about by the increased knowledge breadth of the recruiting organization is much greater than the inhibiting effect due to the fragmentation and uncertainty of R&D resources, but when the KPD Breadth continues to increase beyond the critical value, the magnitude of the effect of these two relationships also reverses.

Research deficiencies and prospects

This study proposes a new perspective of knowledge transfer research based on the knowledge transfer process of inventor mobility, constructs a theoretical model, and uses patent and enterprise data to identify a series of variables describing the characteristics of each subject in this process, and further conducts robustness test by two methods of substitution dependent variable and sub-sample regression to ensure the reliability of the research results and to verify the feasibility of the empirical method of this study. However, there are a series of shortcomings in the study, which need to be further improved in future studies: first, the generalizability of the study findings needs to be further explored. The data samples used in this study are from patent data, i.e., only inventors with patent application records are included in the scope of the study, but in the real situation of mobility, there are a large number of personnel movements that cannot be identified and located by patent data. For example, the mobility of clerical staff, managers, corporate executives, and other inventors without patent output. In the future, the combination of a questionnaire survey and objective data can be considered to construct data for a more comprehensive inventor mobility scenario to verify the reliability of this study again; secondly, the hypothesis model of this study can continue to be improved. For example, competitive relationship and cooperative relationship, or the relationship between upstream and downstream enterprises in the industry chain, as well as the geographical information of enterprises, whether the flow is a cross-country flow behavior, all these information can describe the relationship between the original organization and the recruiting organization in the mobility process, and this relationship will also affect the KTP to a certain extent. In addition to the relationship between the original and recruiting organizations, inventors themselves also have many influencing factors that are worthy of studying the influence of their characteristics on the effect of knowledge transfer, such as information on the network location of inventors' knowledge network in the technical field, information on inventors' part-time social jobs, political identity, social capital, and knowledge capital, etc., and the construction of this theoretical model will be considered in the follow-up.

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